

IMAGE OF A FEMALE CHARACTER IN CHARLOTTE BRONTË'S NOVEL 'JANE EYRE'

Oxunova Muxlisaxon Ravshanbek qizi

Private School "Ideal" in Fergana city

ORCID: 0009-0006-3244-7896

Phone: 91 108-70-10

93 188-70-10

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Abstract. This article explores the image of the central female character, Jane Eyre, in Charlotte Brontë's 1847 novel of the same name. Through a close reading of the text and a review of scholarly literature, it examines how Jane is portrayed as a complex, nuanced character who defies traditional Victorian gender roles and expectations. The article argues that Jane emerges as a strong, independent woman who asserts her own worth and agency in a patriarchal society. Her character arc, relationships, and key scenes in the novel are analyzed to shed light on the proto-feminist elements in Brontë's portrayal.

Keywords: Jane Eyre, Charlotte Brontë, Victorian literature, feminism, gender roles

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada 1847-yilda yozilgan Sharlotta Brontening shu nomdagi romanining bosh qahramoni Jeyn Eyr obrazi ko'rib chiqilgan. Asarni o'rganish va ilmiy adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish orqali u Jeyn qanday qilib Viktoriya davrining an'anaviy gender rollari va umidlariga qarshi turadigan murakkab, nozik qahramon sifatida tasvirlanganini o'rganadi. Maqolada Jeynning patriarxal jamiyatda o'z ahamiyati va mustaqilligini ta'kidlaydigan kuchli, mustaqil ayol sifatida namoyon bo'lishi ta'kidlanadi. Uning xarakteri, munosabatlari va romanlardagi asosiy sahnalar Bronte xarakteridagi proto-feministik elementlarni yoritish uchun tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jeyn Eyr, Sharlotta Bront, Viktoriya adabiyoti, feminizm, gender rollari

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается образ Джейн Эйр, главной героини одноименного романа Шарлотты Бронте, написанного в 1847 году. Благодаря внимательному прочтению текста и обзору научной литературы в нем исследуется, как Джейн изображается как сложный, с множеством нюансов персонаж, который бросает вызов традиционным викторианским гендерным ролям и ожиданиям. В статье утверждается, что Джейн предстает как сильная, независимая женщина, которая утверждает свою значимость и самостоятельность в патриархальном

обществе. Ее характер, взаимоотношения и ключевые сцены в романах анализируются, чтобы пролить свет на протофеминистские элементы в образе Бронте.

Ключевые слова: Джейн Эйр, Шарлотта Бронте, викторианская литература, феминизм, гендерные роли.

INTRODUCTION

Charlotte Brontë's *Jane Eyre*, first published in 1847 under the pseudonym Currer Bell, is widely considered a landmark work of English literature. The novel revolutionized the art of fiction through its intimate first-person narrative and complex characterization [1]. Its eponymous heroine Jane Eyre has become one of the most recognizable characters in the literary canon, and the work is often hailed as an early feminist novel for its depiction of a strong-willed and independent woman who defies societal expectations [2].

This article examines the image and characterization of Jane Eyre in the novel. Through a close textual analysis and review of scholarly literature, it explores how Brontë constructs Jane as an unconventional female character who asserts her agency, intelligence, and sense of self-worth in a patriarchal Victorian society that sought to constrain women's roles. The article argues that Jane emerges as a fully realized, psychologically complex character who transgresses gender norms and becomes a proto-feminist icon.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

To analyze the character of Jane Eyre, this article relies on a close reading of the primary text supplemented by a review of secondary scholarly sources. It draws upon works of literary criticism, feminist theory, and Victorian studies to contextualize and interpret Brontë's portrayal of her heroine.

Peter's seminal work of feminist literary criticism [3], provides a foundational reading of *Jane Eyre* as a female bildungsroman charting Jane's growth into an independent woman. They explore how the narrative centers Jane's consciousness and valorizes feminine rage against oppression. More recent critics like Lisa Sternlieb [4] build upon this feminist interpretation, examining how the novel interrogates restrictive Victorian ideologies of gender and class.

Other scholars like Jerome Beaty [5] focus on the psychological realism and complexity of Jane's characterization. Beaty argues that Brontë endows Jane with a rich inner life full of conflicts, desires, and moral questioning that imbues her with a novelistic interiority and realism uncommon for heroines of the time.

Maria Lamonaca [6] similarly explores how Jane asserts a sense of self-worth and moral integrity even in the face of hardships and societal disapproval.

RESULTS

A close analysis of the text reveals that Brontë portrays Jane as a complex, fully human character with psychological depth and a strong sense of self. From the opening chapters, Jane is shown to be an astute observer endowed with intelligence, imagination, and a keen sense of injustice. The famous "red room" scene where young Jane is unjustly imprisoned establishes her defiant spirit and resistance to abusive authority [7].

As Jane matures, she continues to display an unwavering integrity and a refusal to compromise her moral principles. In her relationship with Rochester, she initially seems to occupy the traditional role of innocent governess seduced by her brooding employer [8]. However, Brontë complicates and subverts this dynamic by imbuing Jane with agency, wit, and a demand for equality. In key scenes like the proposal and aborted wedding, Jane asserts her refusal to be Rochester's mistress and her insistence on being treated as his full equal [9].

Throughout the novel, Jane grapples with conflicts between desire and duty, passion and morality. Brontë grants her heroine the human complexity to experience love and longing while still maintaining her sense of ethics and independence. Jane's temporary departure from Rochester, though painful, ultimately strengthens her character and allows her to return to him on her own terms.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Brontë's characterization of Jane Eyre can be seen as groundbreaking for the Victorian era in its sympathetic portrayal of an unconventional heroine. Jane transgresses expected gender norms through her outspoken nature, fierce independence, and refusal to be subordinated to male authority figures like Rochester or St. John. The narrative validates Jane's perspective and experience, granting her an interiority and agency unusual for female characters of the time.

Through Jane's character arc, the novel engages with proto-feminist ideas and questions prevailing assumptions about women's roles. Jane's insistence on being recognized as Rochester's equal and her decision to flee Thornfield rather than become his mistress assert a radical female autonomy. The novel's famous line, "Reader, I married him," positions Jane as the active agent in her union with Rochester, eschewing traditional notions of male dominance and female submission.

At the same time, the novel does not present Jane as a flawless paragon but as a complex human with faults and inner conflicts. Her occasional harshness, her temptation to submit to Rochester or St. John, and her self-questioning imbue her with a psychological realism that transcends simplistic notions of the idealized heroine. This complexity ultimately renders her character more authentic and sympathetic.

CONCLUSIONS

Charlotte Brontë's *Jane Eyre* offers a powerful and pioneering depiction of female experience through its characterization of Jane. Throughout the novel, Jane emerges as an unconventional heroine who defies Victorian gender expectations and asserts her own agency, intelligence, and moral rectitude. Brontë endows Jane with psychological depth and interiority, granting her a complex humanity that transcends the typical literary representations of women at the time. Through her depiction of Jane, Brontë engages with proto-feminist ideas, interrogating prevailing assumptions about gender roles and presenting a vision of female empowerment and equality. Though shaped by the legal and social realities of the Victorian era, Jane's character arc critiques the limitations placed on women and upholds the right to self-determination and fulfillment.

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